

EXPRESSION AND IMPORTANCE OF UZBEK CHILDREN'S PROSE SAMPLES IN THE NATIONAL CURRICULUM

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The most valuable of the wealth created by each generation and time is a monument that is precious and valuable not only for that time, but also for future times and generations. Prose works are among such riches.

It is difficult to find a country on earth that has not considered the education and development of the young generation as a special problem or has removed this problem from the agenda and taken serious steps in its economic-political, spiritual-educational perspective. History shows that in all countries that have gained their independence, special attention is paid to the education of the young generation as an important condition for strengthening freedom and independence.

In Movarounnahr and many neighboring countries, there are thousands of scientific, moral and technical schools, madrasahs for primary, secondary and higher education that operated until the beginning of the 20th century. and literary works confirm that this issue was considered more seriously in the Muslim East.

It is the logical continuation of those centuries-old traditions that in independent Uzbekistan, education of a mature generation has been treated as one of the issues that cannot be postponed since the first days of independence.

At a time when the world community is worried about political corruption, religious fanaticism, international terrorism, drug addiction, information attack, ecology and many global threats, as the President noted, the weaponization of "Against Ignorance - Enlightenment" and this reform in the process of achieving its effectiveness, it is the sacred duty of each of us to study the rich spiritual heritage of our ancestors, which has been tested for centuries and is important for all times, and to apply it to our social, political, and spiritual life.

There is no stronger force in the world than children. Because they are the owners and creators not only of today, but also of tomorrow. But it is the duty of the older generation to educate this powerful force, bring it to adulthood, and encourage it to take great flights. In this process, first the pre-school educational institution, then the school education, then higher and secondary special educational institutions serve as a place of learning.

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In this regard, the importance of preschool educational institutions and school education is incomparable. The greatest strength that these places rely on is books, more precisely, fiction. Children's poets, writers and dramatists have undertaken the honorable and responsible task of providing these places with a source of knowledge.

This honorable work is manifested in the example of the efforts of modern enlighteners at the beginning of the last century, including the establishment of new schools, the introduction of new educational methods in them, the creation of educational and scientific literature for these educational institutions. had been In this regard, the spiritual courage shown by Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, Hamza Hakimzada Niazi, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov and many other enlighteners is noteworthy. Most importantly, thanks to such efforts, writing special works for children has become a unique tradition in the Turkestan region. This created the basis for the concept of "children's literature" not only as a term, but also as a phenomenon to enter the spiritual life of the country and take a strong place in it.

In the 30s and 50s of the last century, poets and writers such as Gafur Ghulam, Sultan Jora, Zafar Diyar, Shukur Sadulla, Quddus Mohammadi, Qudrat Hikmat created good examples of Uzbek children's literature. Later, such writers as Hakim Nazir, Polat Momin, Nasir Fazilov, Khudoyberdi Tokhtabayev, Akiljon Husanov, Latif Mahmudov, Safar Barnoyev, Tahir Malik, Hojiakbar Shaikhov, Sharaf Bashbekov filled this rank. By the 80s of the last century, the tradition of creating works for children, decided in this way, gave its serious results. Children's poetry and prose, as well as the tradition of creating lyric-epic and dramatic works for them, have also improved. In this process, the services of Khudoiberdi Tokhtaboyev, the people's writer of Uzbekistan, children's favorite writer, are great, of course.

In particular, the writer's works "Sweet Melon Country", "Riding the Yellow Giant", "Death of the Yellow Giant", "A Boy with Five Children", "Mungli Kozlar" are still loved today. . It serves as an important educational material not only for higher education institutions, but also for general education schools.

Family relations is one of the main features of Khudoyberdi Tokhtabayev's writing, which is one of the main features of his art of depicting the complexities of relationships between children and adults.

Indeed, the family is a divine and miraculous discovery of humanity. He is connected to the Motherland by spiritual ties. A person greatly appreciates the motherland where he was born and raised. In particular, the Uzbek people

always remember their responsibility to the family. The role of father and mother in raising a child is different. The fact that examples of the writer's literary heritage, based on such important social facts, are used in the process of ordering elementary school textbooks in general education schools is a proof of the great educational value of the literary work.

In particular, "Native language and reading literacy" for 1st grades published by the Republican Education Center in 2021, organized by the efforts of editors such as Iroda Azimova, Klarakhan Mavlonova, Sadulla Kuronov, Shakir Tursun. a small excerpt from the writer's novel "Riding the Yellow Giant" was included in the textbook. It is worth noting that this passage is not simply attached. Perhaps it was used effectively both as a moral and educational material.

Discussions of the passage begin on page 5 of the textbook with the title "Me, You, Him and Them" and the presentation of the pictures. And on page 6, family photos are presented, and "Look at the pictures. Based on the task "Find words suitable for each", a series of words belonging to the concept of family is presented. These related words such as father, mother, brother, sister, sister, son, grandfather, grandmother, mother, father, grandson, baby, brother, daughter are about the student's family and kinship. serves to strengthen their initial knowledge. Attached at the end of the page is the "Can more than one word fit a picture? Why is that? Who is in your family?" questions such as "synonyms" and "paronyms" will help the student to acquire preliminary knowledge of synonyms and paronyms, and the task "Write words that describe your family members" will help to develop his oral and written speech.

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